

NOISE SHIELDING METAMODELS BASED ON STOCHASTIC RADIAL BASIS FUNCTIONS

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This paper deals with the development of suitable surrogate models for the acoustic assessment of the shielding effects due to engine installation on top of unconventional aircraft configurations. The interest of the aeronautic community towards finding solutions to reduce the environmental impact has increased tremendously in the last decade, in particular to reduce acoustic emissions. The Advisory Council for Aviation Research and Innovation in Europe (ACARE) has in fact set ambitious noise reduction targets for 2050, which can only be reached through important technological advances such as the development of highly innovative configurations. Among solutions proposed in literature, one of the most promising and most investigated is the Blended Wing Body (BWB) aircraft configurations. Because of the peculiar center-body shape of this concept, the engines can be installed on top of the aircraft, making its noise shielding properties particular appealing. Therefore, the choice of the optimal position of the engines to maximize the masking effect represents a crucial aspect that must be taken into account from the early design stages. However, as experimental and historical data are not available in this context, there are no alternative to perform direct simulations for the acoustic assessment needed in conceptual design phase, which would lead to an unacceptable increase of computational resources for optimization purposes. A possible solution is to limit the number of performed simulation by using them to develop metamodels based on stochastic radial basic functions for the evaluation of the acoustic shielding factor, instead of calculating the actual value at each call of the objective functions. Specifically, starting from few high-fidelity simulations by means of a bidimensional integral solver based on the convective Helmholtz equation, an adaptive metamodel is developed for the evaluation of the shielding factor of airfoils, which takes into account the variation of crucial design variables.

Keywords: noise, shielding, metamodels, radial basis functions

1. Introduction

Nowadays, one of the most complex subjects for the aeronautical–community is the mitigation of the noise level produced by aircraft in areas surrounding airports during the take–off and landing operations. Several authorities are involved in pursuing a new strategic road map for aviation research, development and innovation. Focusing on noise control, severe standards impose, the review of the current airport procedures. The FAA has an active program [1], *The Continuous Lower Energy, Emissions, and Noise* (CLEEN) program, for the development of technologies aimed at reducing aircraft noise. In 2016, the *International Civil Aviation Organization’s* (ICAO’s) *Committee on Aviation Environmental Protection* (CAEP) agreed on a new global noise reduction standard as reported in [2]. Some interesting considerations about how the scientific community has been responding to this requests, can be found in [3].

During the last decades, ideas about the noise shielding obtained by installing the engines on top of the fuselage have been conceived for both conventional and innovative aircraft configurations. Results of high–level simulations and experimental campaigns have shown the effectiveness of this strategy in terms of noise shielding [4, 5]. For this reason among others, aviation industry has put a great deal of effort into the design of innovative configurations such as the Blended–Wing–Body (BWB). Studies conducted on this configuration have demonstrated that its large centre body surface shaped as an airfoil contributes to the overall lift force enhancing the aerodynamic efficiency [6], leads itself excellently to the aforementioned on top engine installation [7] and exploit a greater useful volume compared to that of the standard configurations allowing, in principle, the storage of hybrid–electric propulsion power–plant [8]. To maximize the effectiveness of BWB configurations in reducing the perceived noise, a high number of heavy aeroacoustic simulations is required for both configuration and airport procedure optimization. Whereas experimental data about lateral attenuation of conventional configurations is largely available to formulate semi–empirical models, dat about novel configurations can only be retrieved via direct–simulations. This would be excessively cost–demanding in an optimization framework.

Focusing on the airport procedures’ simulations, analysis tools require a large number of evaluation points for the acoustic certification of aircraft in its mission path. To overcome this issue, a robust, reliable and computationally fast alternative to high–fidelity simulations for noise characterization must be developed [9, 10]. Several techniques have been explored to adopt surrogate models to reduce the amount of simulation data: depending on the nature of the problem, the best procedure and tools can be identified [11].

In this work, an approach based on the *Radial Basis Functions* method (RBF) is presented to build a surrogate model (*i.e.*, metamodel) of noise shielding related to an airfoil representing the BWB center–body. It aims at identifying a solid strategy that could be applied to a full scale BWB aircraft geometry. The case study consists of modeling the *Insertion Loss* figure of merit for an integrated array of microphones defined as for certification procedures in one–third octave–bands. This parameter has been evaluated for different positions of a point source located above the airfoil and for different mach values.

The paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 the RBF approach is presented with details about the specific application, the case study is introduced in Section 3, numerical results are presented in Section 4, whereas in Section 5 closes the paper with some concluding remarks.

2. The Radial–Basis–Function formulation

Radial–Basis–Function methods are powerful means to face the problem of reconstructing an unknown function from a set of small data. As it can be found in literature [12], they are particularly suitable for multivariate functions which are: i) dependent on many variables or parameters; ii) defined by many data; iii) described by scattered data in their domain. An original dynamic metamodeling ap-

proach based on the use of a generalized Radial Basis Functions (RBF) is herein proposed. The general form of the basis function is

$$\varphi(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\eta}) = |\boldsymbol{\xi} - \boldsymbol{\eta}|^\alpha \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ are two points of the design space. The surrogate deterministic and stochastic models for the function $f(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ are respectively defined as

$$\hat{f}_D(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_T} w_j \varphi(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\xi}_j), \quad \alpha = 3 \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{f}_S(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = EV \left[\sum_{j=1}^{N_T} w_j \varphi(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\xi}_j) \right], \quad \alpha \sim \text{unif} [\alpha_{min} : \alpha_{max}] \quad (3)$$

$$(4)$$

where the $\boldsymbol{\xi}_j$ is one of the training points, and the weights w_j are obtained imposing $\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi}_j) = f(\boldsymbol{\xi}_j)$. The condition for the surrogate model to reproduce the training set yields the system of equations for the unknowns w_j

$$\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{p} \quad (5)$$

with $A_{ij} = \varphi(\boldsymbol{\xi}_i, \boldsymbol{\xi}_j)$. For the stochastic approach, the α power of the Euclidean distance is used as kernel function, *i.e.* the stochastic parameter, imposing a uniform distribution in its range ($P(\alpha) = \text{const}$). The stochastic parameter has been sampled using a *Monte Carlo* method with 100 samples to guarantee the statistic convergence.

The advantage of using a stochastic formulation is the evaluation of the local uncertainty of the model that can be used to drive the improvement of the training set with new samples in the more uncertain regions. This uncertainty is quantified as the difference of the relevant p -quantiles of the predictions obtained varying the α parameter so as to have a 95%–confidence band

$$U_{\hat{f}}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = q(p_1, \boldsymbol{\xi}) - q(p_2, \boldsymbol{\xi}) \quad (6)$$

with $p_1 = 0.975$ and $p_2 = 0.025$. Adopting a dynamic update of the metamodel based on stochastic formulation $\hat{f}_S(\boldsymbol{\xi})$, at each iteration the training set is updated with an additional sample obtained exploring the variables domain by means of a genetic algorithm. The objective function for the search algorithm is the maximum uncertainty in prediction of the current surrogate model. Once the point is collected, equation (5) is evaluated and the prediction on the test set points re-computed. The convergence value for the uncertainty has been set as a percentage of the y -range of the IL function

$$U_{conv} = 0.02(\max[f(\boldsymbol{\xi})] - \min[f(\boldsymbol{\xi})]) \quad (7)$$

3. Case study

Existing aircraft noise prediction tools allow the computation of noise contours around airports as well as the noise certification levels, starting from aircraft tracks (in terms of altitude, speed, thrust and general configuration) and airport layout. From a broader viewpoint, a noise prediction tool can help the aircraft designer, and consequently the aviation industries, to drive markets towards increasingly eco-sustainable choices. In order to include the new BWB aircraft concepts within the well-assessed prediction tools, a feasible strategy could be providing a correction for the existing NPD (Noise-Power-Distance) curves, which represent a standard technique for evaluating the noise impact due to flight procedures. The NPD

relationship provides noise levels as a function of observer distance via spherical spreading through a standard atmosphere, with suitable corrections to account for specific single-event metric (under standard meteorological conditions). Noise levels are integrated over the microphones array to yield a single value instead of instantaneous sound pressure level so as to represent the noise produced by infinite flight-path with constant height and speed [13].

Figure 1: The case study is the noise shielding of an airfoil geometry with unitary chord in presence of a uniform flow.

The acoustic describer for the noise shielding effect characterization is the Insertion Loss (IL). In the frequency domain, it can be defined as it follows

$$IL = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\tilde{p}_I}{\tilde{p}_T} \right) = SPL_I - SPL_T \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{p}_T = \tilde{p}_I + \tilde{p}_S$ is the total pressure, \tilde{p}_I the incident pressure, \tilde{p}_S the scattered pressure and SPL is the sound pressure level. Pressure data are computed through numerical simulations using a boundary integral formulation to solve the exterior boundary value problem for the convected Helmholtz equation. Specifically, a validated in-house code has been used which implements a zero-th order boundary element method based on the collocation method.

Following this guidelines, a preliminary study is herein presented, with the aim at investigating the functional dependencies of IL with respect to the source-observer distance, the source position and aircraft speed. The benchmark consists in a unit point source emitting in an acoustic field in presence of a uniform flow (see Fig.1). The target function is therefore represented by the IL at a virtual microphone, whereas the independent variables domain is represented by the source location \mathbf{x}_s (above the lifting surface) and the Mach number \mathbf{x}_M . The design space bounds are $-0.5 < \mathbf{x}_s < 0.5$ (leading edge and trailing edge of the airfoil) and $0.1 < \mathbf{x}_M < 0.3$.

In order to show the results of the shielding effect due to an airfoil in far-field, a convergence analysis has been carried out varying the distance between a circular array of microphones and the point source as a function of $kr = \frac{2\pi f}{c_0} r$ where $r = nc$ is referred to the airfoil chord c . In Fig.2, the correlation functions for three bands ($f_c = 500Hz, 1000Hz, 1600Hz$) are reported. A unitary value of the correlation function means that the IL at the current distance has the same pattern as for the distance depicted as ∞ . This analysis guarantees that the distance can be excluded from the design variables.

Figure 2: Correlation functions for $f_c = 315, 1000, 1600$. The highlighted point is the chosen distance at which the simulations have been carried out.

4. Results and discussion

In this section, the results obtained using the aforementioned strategy are presented for the one-third octave bands $f_c = 315\text{Hz}$ and $f_c = 1600\text{Hz}$. As introduced above, the IL value for each point of the design space is integrated in one-third octave band and over the microphones array placed at far-field distance. For each of these bands uncertainty value, standard deviation, true function and metamodel prediction are evaluated at 1500 evenly spaced points of the design space, which do not correspond to any point used to train the metamodel.

In Fig.3 the convergence trends are shown as a function of the dynamic surrogate model update, *i.e.* the number of points added to the training set. It is worth noting that for the band $f_c = 315\text{Hz}$, the maximum uncertainty within the prediction points evolves smoother than for $f_c = 1600\text{Hz}$. This is due to the position of the initial training set points that already capture the two lobes pattern of the true function helping the uncertainty level to decrease regularly (see Fig.4 and 5). Whereas, as the irregularity of the function increases like in $f_c = 1600\text{Hz}$, adding new samples to the training set implies an increment of the local uncertainty until the pattern of the true function is not yet captured by the metamodel. Strictly speaking, the algorithm tends to add new samples in regions where the function exhibits the maximum curvature. Indeed, in these regions varying the value of the stochastic parameter of the metamodel kernel returns different prediction values, *i.e.*, a high uncertainty, as far as the current points in that area do not represent the function qualitatively. This effect becomes remarkable for the high frequency bands (the function becomes more wavy) justifying the higher number of points needed to reach the convergence.

The power of this method lies in the fact that an improvement of the metamodel can be achieved using the uncertainty quantification of the metamodel itself. This is very useful for all that problems in which the true function is unknown and few scattered data is available.

Finally, for both cases, it can be said the RBF approach succeeded in reproducing the IL pattern within the design space with a good approximation, using a limited number of training points. In Table 1, the main results are reported also for intermediate frequency bands. A maximum prediction error of about 21% has been detected for the band 315Hz using the final metamodel. It corresponds to an error of about 0.13 dB on IL, which is negligible for aeroacoustic applications. It is interesting to note that for the band $f_c = 500\text{Hz}$ the final metamodel computes the lower error of prediction (corresponding to 0.068 dB). Results for this band are shown in Fig.7.

Figure 3: Uncertainty quantification as a function of dynamic model update. For $f_c = 315Hz$, a convergence value of 0.043 has been reached with 118 points of TS. For $f_c = 1600Hz$, a convergence value of 0.038 has been reached with 578 points of TS.

Figure 4: Adaptive, stochastic metamodel evolution for the one-third octave band with $f_c = 315Hz$

Figure 5: Adaptive, stochastic metamodel evolution for the one-third octave band with $f_c = 1600Hz$

Figure 6: Residual error of prediction using the final metamodells. For $f_c = 315Hz$, a maximum error lower than 22% is computed. For $f_c = 1600Hz$, a maximum error lower than 10% is computed.

Table 1: Results for the other one-third octave bands.

f_c [Hz]	315	400	500	630	800	1000	1250	1600
Convergence	0.043	0.043	0.037	0.041	0.037	0.034	0.038	0.038
No. of TS points	118	114	169	294	245	427	457	578
Max. Rel. error [%]	21.2	18.2	7.2	8.6	9.9	8.3	10.6	9.9

Figure 7: Metamodel for $f_c = 500Hz$

5. Conclusions

In this work, an approach for the noise shielding evaluation of unconventional aircraft configurations has been proposed. A simple benchmark where an airfoil geometry has been placed between the point source and the microphones' array to measure its scattering effect in presence of a uniform flow has been measured through the IL figure of merit. The design variables considered are the Mach number and the point source position (corresponding to the engine installation position). Few training set points, in which the exact value of IL has been calculated via high-fidelity simulations, has been used to build a metamodel by means of a stochastic and adaptive RBF method. This approach allows the designer to reduce the computational burden required to perform airport procedure and configuration optimization by substituting direct simulations with the obtained metamodel for the numerous evaluations of the objective function. It has been proved that using stochastic RBF, a reliable and accurate model of the IL noise shielding can be built using a limited number of direct-simulations. The error computed by the final version of the metamodel (using the training set points found by the genetic research algorithm to reach

the imposed convergence) is negligible for all the one-third octave bands considered.

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